

Validation of Sir Ganga Ram Hospital Prostate Symptoms Score (SGRH-PSS), compared with the International Prostate Symptoms Score (IPSS) in assessing lower urinary tract symptoms in the clinical setting

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Abstract

Aim: To validate Sir Ganga Ram Hospital Prostate Symptoms score (SGRHPSS), versus the International Prostate Symptoms Score (IPSS) in assessing lower urinary tract symptoms in the clinical setting.

Material & Methods: Male patients with age ≥ 45 years presented with lower urinary tract symptoms in OPD or admitted in wards were included. Female patients and male patients with age < 45 years were excluded. Sample size was calculated using the formula $(Z^2 \times p \times q) / d^2$ and 560 cases of lower urinary tract symptoms (LUTS) were included. Each patient filled both IPSS and SGRH-PSS questionnaire. Each patient underwent ultrasound for prostate size, residual urine and uroflowmetry. Both scoring systems were compared, also with objective parameters of LUTS i.e., ultrasound findings for prostate size, post voided residual urine (PVRU) and uroflowmetry.

Settings and Design: The study was conducted at department of Urology, Institute of Renal Sciences at Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, New Delhi. It was a prospective and comparative study. The study was conducted from July 2014 to March 2016.

Statistical Analysis: We measured reliability of SGRHPSS using test-retest correlation coefficient 29 and Cronbach's Alpha 29, 30 for internal consistency. All analysis was conducted using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences 20 (SPSS 20) software.

Results: Total IPSS score ranged from 2 to 34 with mean score of 18, while voiding LUTS ranged from 0 to 20 with mean score of 10.89 and storage LUTS ranged from 1 to 15 with mean score of 7.12. Total SGRHPSS score ranged from 1 to 8 with mean score of 5.79, while voiding LUTS ranged from 0 to 4 with mean score of 3.0 and storage LUTS ranged from 0 to 4 with mean score of 2.79. Spearman coefficient correlation in between total IPSS score and SGRHPSS score was 0.927 (P value < 0.001) and QoL in IPSS and SGRHPSS was 0.867 (P value < 0.001) suggest statistically significant and strong positive relationship.

Conclusion: After analysing above observations and results, we concluded that SGRHPSS score system is shorter, efficient, friendlier, and less cumbersome for patients and clinicians and may potentially replace or compliment the IPSS.

Keywords: Sir Ganga Ram Hospital Prostate Symptoms Score (SGRH-PSS), International Prostate Symptoms Score (IPSS), Lower Urinary Tract Symptoms (LUTS).

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Introduction

Benign prostate hyperplasia (BPH) is a common benign urologic condition in men, and its prevalence increases with age. [1] The enlarged gland has been proposed to cause lower urinary tract symptoms (LUTS) complex via at least two routes: (1) direct bladder outlet obstruction (BOO) from enlarged tissue (static component) and (2) from increased smooth muscle tone and resistance within the enlarged gland (dynamic component). [2] LUTS comprise storage or irritative symptoms, including frequency, nocturia, urgency and urge

incontinence as well as voiding or obstructive symptoms, such as weak urinary stream, straining, hesitancy, and intermittency. [3,4]

Several symptom scoring systems have been developed, including the Boyarsky [5] and Madsen- Iversen [6]. These questionnaires are not designed to be self-administered, which may introduce an interviewer bias. These symptom scores neither identify the bother of symptoms, their impact on quality of life, nor studied for their reliability and validity [7]. Two score systems, the

American Urological Association Symptom Index (AUASI) and the Danish Prostatic Symptom Score (DAN-PSS) system was then validated [8,9]. The International Prostate Symptom score (IPSS), uses the same seven questions assessing LUTS severity as the AUASI, plus an eighth disease specific quality of life (QOL) question that assesses the

bother associated with LUTS, was adopted by the WHO in 1993 [10]. The 2003 American Urological Association (AUA) guideline on BPH also advocates the use of the American Urological Association Symptoms Score/Index (AUASS/AUASI) [11].

Table 1: International Prostate Symptom Score (IPSS)

Symptoms (In the last month)	Not at all	Less than 1 in 5 Times	Less than half the Time	About Half The Time	More than Half the Time	Almost Always	Your score
1. Incomplete Emptying How often have you had the sensation of not emptying your bladder?							
2. Frequency How often have you had to urinate less than every two hours?							
3. Intermittency How often have you found you stopped and started again several times when you urinated?							
4. Urgency How often have you found it difficult to postpone urination?							
5. Weak Stream How often have you had a weak urinary stream?							
6. Straining How often have you had to strain to start urination?							
	None	1 Time	2 Time	3 Times	4 Times	5 Times	
7. Nocturia How many times did you typically get up at night to urinate?							
Total I-PSS Score							

Categories of LUTS	Mild	Moderate	Severe
Total score	0-7	8-19	20-35

Quality of life due to Urinary Symptoms (Bothersome)	Delighted	Pleased	Mostly satisfied	Mixed	Mostly Dissatisfied	Unhappy	Terrible
If you were to spend the rest of your life with your urinary condition just the way it is now, how would you feel about that?	0	1	2	3	4	5	6

Although beneficial from a clinical standpoint, the AUASS or IPSS has certain shortcomings. Major shortcoming of IPSS questionnaire is lengthy, complicated, and cumbersome wordings that has to be filled by the patients, especially the choices of occurrence of symptoms in relation to time the

questionnaire can be misunderstood and misinterpreted [12,13].

To resolve this problem, a shorter, modified version of the AUASS was developed by some authors termed as a UWIN (urgency, weak stream, incomplete emptying and nocturia) to reduce the burden of the AUASS questionnaire [14,15,16].

We have developed another modified scoring system which we presume to be simpler, more patients friendly and more practical, Sir Ganga

Ram Hospital Prostate Symptom Score (SGRHPSS) at our institution to reduce the burden of the AUA-SS questionnaire.

Table 2: Sir Ganga Ram Hospital Prostate Symptoms Score (SGRHPSS).

In last one month			
Incomplete Emptying Do you unable to empty your bladder completely?	Absent Score - 0	Present Score - 1	
Frequency How often you have to urinate during the day?	Less than 7 Score - 0	7 or more than 7 Score - 1	
Nocturia How many times did you regularly get up at night to urinate?	0 Score - 0	1-2 Score 1	≥ 3 Score 2
Urgency Do you found it difficult to postpone urination?	Never Score 0	Present Score 1	
Intermittent Flow Do you found it stopped and started again several times when you urinated?	Absent Score 0	Present Score 1	
Weak Stream How is your urinary stream?	Good Score 0	Poor Score 1	
Straining Do you have to strain to pass urine?	Absent Score 0	Present Score 1	

Total SGR-PSS Score	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
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LUTS category: - 0: Normal 1-2: Mild LUTS 3-5: Moderate LUTS 6-8: Severe LUTS

Quality of life due to Urinary Symptoms	Pleased-satisfied	Variable	Miserable
If you were to spend the rest of your life with your urinary condition just the way it is now, how would you feel about that?	0	1	2

Aims and Objective

To Validate Sir Ganga Ram Hospital Prostate Symptoms Score (SGRHPSS), versus The International Prostate Symptoms Score (IPSS) in Assessing Lower Urinary Tract Symptoms in the Clinical Setting.

Material and Methods

Study Site: Department of Urology, Institute of Renal Sciences at the Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, New Delhi.

Study Population: Male patients with age ≥ 45 years presented with lower urinary tract symptoms in OPD or admitted in wards of our hospital, who full filled inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Study Design: Prospective and Comparative study of the efficacy of the SGRH-PSS in assessment of LUTS compared with that of the IPSS.

Sample Size Calculation: Sample size was calculated using the formula $(Z^2 \times p \times q) / d^2$. When we expected that correlation of SGRH-PSS in evaluation of lower urinary tract symptoms, correlating their findings with The Gold Standard IPSS with $(p) = 85\%$, precision error of estimation

$(d) = 0.03$, and $\alpha = 0.05$, a sample size of 550 cases will be needed.

Sample Size: 560 cases of lower urinary tract symptoms (LUTS) were included in this study.

Period of Study: The prospective study started from July 2014 (after getting approval from ethical committee) to March 2016 to recruit 560 cases of LUTS.

Inclusion Criteria: Male patients with age ≥ 45 years presented with lower urinary tract symptoms in OPD or admitted in wards.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Female patients
2. Male patients with age < 45 years

Methodology

We started our study after clearance from ethical committee to recruit patients of lower urinary tract symptom who fulfilled inclusion criteria and exclusion criteria. Each patient filled both IPSS and SGRH-PSS questionnaire. Using closed enveloped system 50% patients filled IPSS questionnaire first then SGRH-PSS questionnaire and remaining 50% patients filled SGRH-PSS questionnaire first then

IPSS questionnaire. Score system categorized according to total score and patient divided in mild, moderate, and severe category of LUTS in both scoring systems. Each patient answered a question that which scoring system was easy to understand and easy to fill. Each patient underwent ultrasound for prostate size, residual urine and uroflowmetry. In the last we compared both scoring system with objective parameter of LUTS i.e. ultrasound findings for prostate size, post voided residual urine (PVRU) and uroflowmetry.

Statistical Analysis: In our study we measured reliability of SGRHPSS using test-retest correlation coefficient 29 and Cronbach's Alpha 29, 30 for

internal consistency. We planned to validate our score by comparing total score, categories of LUTS and QOL question of SGRHPSS with total score, categories of LUTS and QOL question of IPSS. We measured Spearman correlation coefficient 31 for correlation among IPSS and SGRHPSS. We measured agreement between total score and QOL question of IPSS and SGRHPSS using Bland Altman plots. 32, 33 We also measured correlation of IPSS and SGRHPSS with objective parameter of LUTS i.e. ultrasound findings for prostate size, post void residual urine (PVRU) and uroflowmetry parameter. All analysis conducted using IBM SPSS 20 software.

Flow Chart 1

Results and Discussion

Out of 560 patients, maximum i.e., 36.1% patients belonged to age group 61-70 years. Mean age was 64.93 years and age ranged from 45 year to 98 years. Mean prostate size was 41.83cc (range 10-170cc), mean PVRU was 89.67cc (range 0-601cc), mean Qmax (maximum urinary flow rate in uroflowmetry) was 11.14 ml/sec (range 1.0-38.0 ml/sec), mean Qavg (average urinary flow rate in uroflowmetry) was 6.05 ml/sec (range 0.6-23.8 ml/sec). 8.9% patients belonged to mild LUTS in IPSS, 41.1% belonged to moderate LUTS in IPSS and 50% belonged to severe LUTS in IPSS. 8.8% patients belonged to mild LUTS in SGRHPSS, 33.6% belonged to moderate LUTS in SGRHPSS and 57.7% belonged to severe LUTS in SGRHPSS.

Out 50 patients with mild LUTS in IPSS, 49 patients were in mild LUTS in SGRHPSS while only 1 patient in moderate LUTS in SGRHPSS. 230 patients were with moderate LUTS in IPSS, out of these 187 patients were in mild LUTS in SGRHPSS and 43 patients were in severe LUTS in SGRHPSS. All 280 patients with severe LUTS in IPSS also belonged to severe LUTS in SGRHPSS. Spearman coefficient correlation was 0.888 in between IPSS and SGRHPSS categories showed strong correlation in two score systems (P value <0.001).

For test-retest reliability same respondents filled SGRHPSS twice after one week. Total scores on the two occasions were then correlated using Pearson's test-retest-reliability coefficient.

Table 3: Reliability statistics measuring test-retest reliability coefficient.

	Total SGRHPSS score first time fill	Total SGRHPSS score second time fill	P value <0.001
Total SGRHPSS score first time fill	1	0.914	
Total SGRHPSS score second time fill	0.914	1	

Test-retest reliability coefficient of this study was 0.914, which indicates excellent test-retest reliability of SGRHPSS.

Table 4: Correlation of LUTS category in IPSS and SGRHPSS.

IPSS category	SGRHPSS category			Total Number of patients	P Value <0.001	Spearman correlation coefficient 0.888
	Mild	Moderate	Severe			
Mild	49	1	0	50		
Moderate	0	187	43	230		
Severe	0	0	280	280		
Total number of patients	49	188	323	560		

There were 50 patients with mild LUTS in IPSS. Out of these 50 patients, 49 patients were in mild LUTS in SGRHPSS while only 1 patient was in moderate LUTS in SGRHPSS. There were 230 patients with moderate LUTS in IPSS. Out of these 230 patients, 187 patients were in mild LUTS in SGRHPSS, and 43 patients were in severe LUTS in

SGRHPSS. There were 280 patients with severe LUTS in IPSS. All these patients also belonged to severe LUTS in SGRHPSS. Spearman coefficient correlation in between IPSS category and SGRHPSS category shows strong correlation in two score system (0.888).

Table 5: Correlation in between total score, LUTS categories and QOL in IPSS and SGRHPSS.

	Total IPSS score	IPSS category	QOL in IPSS	Total SGRHPSS score	SGRHPSS category	QOL in SGRHPSS	P value <0.001
Total IPSS score	1.000	0.898	0.822	0.927	0.861	0.839	
IPSS category	0.898	1.000	0.792	0.875	0.888	0.859	
QOL in IPSS	0.822	0.792	1.000	0.764	0.782	0.867	
Total SGRHPSS score	0.927	0.875	0.764	1.000	0.893	0.819	
SGRHPSS category	0.861	0.888	0.782	0.893	1.000	0.843	
QOL in SGRHPSS	0.839	0.859	0.867	0.819	0.843	1.000	

Spearman coefficient correlation >0.70 indicate strong correlation. Above table showed strong correlation in between total IPSS score, IPSS categories, QOL in IPSS, Total SGRHPSS score,

SGRHPSS category and QOL in SGRHPSS. P value <.001 for all correlation suggestive of statistically significant correlation.

Table 6: Correlation in between individual symptoms in IPSS and SGRHPSS.

	Incomplete emptying in SGRH	Frequency in SGRH	Intermittency in SGRH	Urgency in SGRH	Weak Stream in SGRH	Straining in SGRH	Nocturia in SGRH
Incomplete emptying in IPSS	0.864	0.361	0.368	0.204	0.265	0.368	0.396
Frequency in IPSS	0.330	0.666	0.219	0.286	0.241	0.276	0.441
Intermittency in IPSS	0.388	0.246	0.824	0.178	0.247	0.469	0.413
Urgency in IPSS	0.192	0.185	0.170	0.947	0.032	0.122	0.312
Weak stream in IPSS	0.390	0.360	0.438	0.136	0.469	0.632	0.436
Straining in IPSS	0.369	0.327	0.450	0.122	0.353	0.792	0.400
Nocturia in IPSS	0.440	0.403	0.399	0.317	0.324	0.441	0.902

Above table showed that there was a strong correlation between incomplete emptying, intermittency, urgency, straining and nocturia question of IPSS and SGRHPSS, good correlation in between frequency and weak stream. These

questions were retained in final SGRHPSS questionnaire because deleting this question can leads to low alpha which means low internal consistency of questionnaire.

Table 7: Distribution of patients according to USG findings of Prostate Size, PVRU and Uroflowmetry parameters.

	Mean \pm SD	Median	Minimum - Maximum
USG for Prostate size in cc	41.83 \pm 22.74	37.40	10 - 170
USG for PVRU in cc	89.67 \pm 93.73	64.00	0 - 601
Qmax in ml/sec	11.14 \pm 5.97	10.00	1.0 - 38.0
Qavg in ml/sec	6.05 \pm 3.58	5.30	0.6 - 23.8

In our study mean prostate size in trans-abdominal ultrasonography was 41.83cc, minimum size was 10cc while maximum size was 170cc. In our study mean post void residual urine volume in ultrasonography was 89.67cc, minimum was 0cc while maximum was 601cc.

Mean Qmax (maximum urinary flow rate in uroflowmetry) was 11.14 ml/sec, minimum was 1.0 ml/sec while maximum was 38.0 ml/sec. Mean Qavg (average urinary flow rate in uroflowmetry) was 6.05 ml/sec, minimum was 0.6 ml/sec while maximum was 23.8 ml/sec.

Cronbach alpha in our study is .743 including 7 questions, measured using SPSS software.

Table 8: Reliability statistics measuring Cronbach's alpha for SGRHPSS.

Questions included in SGRHPSS	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Incomplete emptying	0.698
Frequency	0.718
Intermittency	0.700
Urgency	0.761
Weak stream	0.731
Straining	0.692
Nocturia	0.677

While addition of eight question that is our modified quality of life questionnaire, gives Cronbach

alpha 0.821, which makes our score more reliable more consistent.

Questions included in SGRHPSS	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Incomplete emptying	0.800
Frequency	0.810
Intermittency	0.797
Urgency	0.836

Weak stream	0.816
Straining	0.792
Nocturia	0.787
Quality of life	0.743

Above table conformed that deleting any item other than urgency question can leads to decrease value of alpha i.e., decrease internal consistency of SGRHPSS. Deletion of urgency question can lead

to slight gain in alpha but this symptom retained in final scoring system due to its strong correlation with IPSS urgency question (Spearman coefficient correlation 0.94

Figure 1: Bland Altman Plot for correlation in between total IPSS and SGRHPSS.

Bland Altman Plot in between total IPSS and SGRHPSS showed good agreement in between total IPSS and total SGRHPSS.

Figure 2: Bland Altman Plot for correlation in between QOL in IPSS and SGRHPSS.

Bland Altman Plot in between QOL in IPSS and SGRHPSS, showed good agreement in between QOL in IPSS and SGRHPSS.

In our study total IPSS ranged from 2 to 34 with mean score of 18, voiding LUTS in IPSS ranged from 0 to 20 with mean score of 10.89 and storage LUTS in IPSS ranged from 1 to 15 with mean score of 7.12. Dividing patient with LUTS category in IPSS, 8.9% patients belonged to mild LUTS, 41.1% belonged to moderate LUTS in IPSS and 50% belonged to severe LUTS. Total SGRHPSS ranged from 1 to 8 with mean score of 5.79, voiding LUTS in SGRHPSS ranged from 0 to 4 with mean score of 3.0 and storage LUTS in SGRHPSS ranged from 0 to 4 with mean score of 2.79. Dividing patient with LUTS category in SGRHPSS, 8.8% patients belonged to mild LUTS, 33.6% belonged to moderate LUTS and 57.7% belonged to severe LUTS.

We performed reliability test by two methods. One was using test-retest reliability in which same patients filled questionnaire after one week and Pearson correlation coefficient measured, which is 0.914 in our study, which showed excellent retest reliability. Other method of reliability was test for internal consistency measuring cronbach alpha, which is 0.743 including 7 questions of LUTS symptoms, while addition modified quality of life questionnaire, gives Cronbach alpha .821, which suggest that our score system is reliable and consistent.

While correlating IPSS with SGRHPSS in our study, there were 50 patients with mild LUTS in

IPSS. Out of these 50 patients, 49 patients were in mild LUTS in SGRHPSS while only 1 patient was in moderate LUTS in SGRHPSS. There were 230 patients with moderate LUTS in IPSS. Out of these 230 patients, 187 patients were in mild LUTS in SGRHPSS, and 43 patients were in severe LUTS in SGRHPSS. There were 280 patients with severe LUTS in IPSS. All these patients also belonged to severe LUTS in SGRHPSS. Spearman coefficient correlation in between total IPSS score and SGRHPSS score was 0.927, IPSS category and SGRHPSS category was 0.888 and QOL in IPSS and SGRHPSS was 0.867 with P value <0.001 for all above correlation, suggestive of statistically significant correlation. The Spearman correlation coefficient between the IPSS and the SGRHPSS at the level of total score, category, and QOL question showed a strong positive relationship.

Correlation coefficients measure the strength of the linear relationship between the two-scoring system of a patient who responded to each questionnaire (IPSS and SGRHPSS). Our evaluation revealed a good linear relationship between total scores, score categories and QOL questions of SGRHPSS and IPSS. However, when evaluating a new questionnaire verses an established instrument, we must see whether the new instrument agrees with the older questionnaire. So, we performed a second analysis using Bland-Altman [17,18] plots to further evaluate the agreement between the 2 questionnaires. The Bland-Altman plot is a graphical method to compare two measurement techniques, and it is an established evaluation tool used to determine agreement between 2

measurement techniques. This method requires that the scores of the 2 instruments be expressed on the same scale. In this graphical method the differences between the two techniques are plotted against the average of the two techniques. The both the system was said to be in agreement if the values plotted are lies within the 95% confidence limit.

In this study the Bland-Altman plots between total IPSS and SGRHPSS showed good agreement (Fig 7). This indicates that even after changing answer options, the SGRHPSS demonstrates a similar degree of utility as the IPSS. This supports the notion that the shorter SGRHPSS questionnaire can be used in place of the longer IPSS. A good agreement also seen between QOL in IPSS and SGRHPSS, indicating that decreasing the QOL answer options did not alter the value of the QOL question

Conclusion

We introduced a simplified form of the IPSS questionnaire called SGRHPSS. We validated the SGRHPSS questionnaire using statistical analysis. Our score is reliable as test-retest reliability coefficient in our study is 0.914 and internally consistent (Cronbach alpha) is 0.821. Spearman coefficient correlation in between total IPSS and SGRHPSS is 0.927, IPSS and SGRHPSS categories are 0.888 and QOL in IPSS and SGRHPSS is 0.867 (P value <0.001 for all above correlation), suggestive of statistically significant correlation. The Spearman correlation coefficient between the IPSS and the SGRHPSS at the level of total score, categories, and QOL question showed a strong positive relationship. The Bland-Altman plots between total IPSS and SGRHPSS and in between QOL in IPSS and SGRHPSS shows good agreement. Our results indicate that shortening the IPSS questionnaire and QOL answer options did not alter the value of the SGRHPSS questionnaire. Correlation coefficient with total IPSS is 0.231 with prostate size, .599 with PVRU, -0.624 with Qmax and -0.586 with Qavg while correlation coefficient with total SGRHPSS is 0.235 with prostate size, .580 with PVRU, -0.554 with Qmax and -0.540 with Qavg. In our study all the participants said that SGRHPSS is easy to understand and easy to fill.

So, we concluded that our score system is shorter, efficient, friendlier, and less burdensome for patients and clinicians and may potentially replace the IPSS.

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